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Effect of Play-Way Method on Academic performance among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State

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Abstract

This study examined the Effect of Play-Way Method on Academic performance among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State. The study objectives were: to determine the effect of play way method and conventional teaching method in the pretest mean scores among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis To determined Performance of pupils taught using Play-way method and those exposed to conventional method in Gombe metropolis and to Determine Performance of male and female pupils taught using Play-way teaching method Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The study adopted quasi experimental research design. The participants in the study comprised of 45 pupils from two Nursery Schools in Gombe metropolis. Convenience sampling technique was uses in drawing the participants. The data was analyzed using T-test, The findings obtained from the research showed that pupils in the control group had slightly higher initial scores on the pre-test mean scores compared to the experimental group in the pretest, also, experimental group is superior to control group in facilitating achievement among pupils in the post test, finally there is no significant difference in the gender difference of the posttest analysis using the experimental group. The study concluded that given the extensive developmental benefits that play gives during a child's early years, the play-way approach is the most suitable way for children in early childhood programs to develop and learn Recommended that Educators should incorporate more play-based learning activities into their curriculum.

Keywords: Play-Way, Teaching Method, Performance, Nursery Schools and Pupils

Introduction

Teaching is a key component of education, Paolo et al. (2013) defined teaching in the concept of education as the concerted sharing of knowledge and experience, which is usually organized within a discipline and, more generally, the provision of stimulus to the psychological and intellectual growth of a person by another person or artifact and according to Wikipedia (Teaching, 2023) Teaching is the practice implemented by a teacher aimed at transmitting skills (knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills) to a learner, a student, or any other audience in the context of an educational institution. According to Al-Shuaibi (2014), education is a methodical process that exposes people to and gives them the chance to acquire knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that all work together to prepare them for successful integration into society, career pursuits, and a lifelong love of learning.

Professional teachers with plenty of expertise should be aware of the best teaching strategies to apply at each stage of the teaching-learning process. The pre-primary, primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of our educational system should be taught by qualified and experienced teachers who understand what and how to teach at each level. Because of the immaturity of the child at pre-primary level, professional teachers must take care to employ the practical method or methods of instruction as supported by (Oluseyi & Ishola, 2015). At the early childhood stage, teachers should employ methods that will help them learn the things they need to learn instead of confusing them and making them incapable of learning.

Play-away method is a great way to teach tender children since it stimulates their interest in the subjects they are studying. The child can also practice what they learn in class by using the role-playing approach of instruction (Fesseha & Pyle, 2016). The reason for this is that while a child learning through group activities can learn from peers, the role that a youngster performs during instruction in the classroom is permanently ingrained in their brain. This approach is excellent because It enables the child to improve various skills like motor, creative, imaginative, aesthetic, cognitive and linguistic (Kanal, 2018).

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Many findings from recent studies on the effectiveness of teachers should be of interest to people who work with tender children, especially in the primary grades (Prout & James, 2015). These studies' findings were not conclusive, but they do give a decent picture of how successful teachers function in the classroom. This is not to argue that early childhood education cannot benefit from the adoption of child-centered teaching strategies. Sometimes these methods are necessary to accomplish specific curriculum objectives. However, research indicates that it would be wise to go back to the fundamentals when it comes to curriculum and teaching methods for early childhood education (Ameena, 2020). The results of significant studies carried out in the United States and Great Britain provide evidence in favor of conventional approaches to teaching fundamental skills. Perhaps a definition of "traditional" would be helpful. This does not imply that all of the lessons in the class must follow a strict schedule. The term as it is used here refers to small group instruction under the direction of the teacher.

Therefore, although nothing radically new or unique is proposed by the current findings, it could be prudent to adjust established methods if they are to be helpful in supporting the learning of young children. Undoubtedly, it is in the light of these factors that an investigation into teaching styles in early childhood education especially Nursery Schools in Gombe metropolis was conducted with the goal of resolving issues related to the incorrect selection of instructional philosophies and methods for in Nursery Schools.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to determine the effect of play way method academic performance among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought:

- 1 To determine performance of pupils taught using Play-way method and those exposed to conventional method in Gombe metropolis
- 2 To Determine Performance of male and female pupils taught using Play-way teaching method Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of play way method and conventional teaching method in the pre-test mean scores of pupils among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis?
2. What is the mean Performance scores of pupils taught using Play-way method and those exposed to conventional method in Gombe metropolis?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between mean Performance scores of male and female pupils taught using Play-way method in Gombe metropolis

Methodology

The research design employed in this study was experimental research design was quasi-experimental design. The specific design used for the study was a pretest posttest non-equivalent control group design. There is an experimental group (where pupils were taught using play way method) and a control group. The study's participants were 45 pupils drawn from two schools in Gombe metropolis (Kingdom Heritage Model School, Gombe and Dominion groups of school). For this study, two Nursery schools in the Gombe metropolis were selected using convenience sampling technique. A coin toss determined which school was placed in the treatment group and which school was placed in the control group. In each school that was drawn for this study all the intact classes of pre nursery were used for the study.

To gather data, the researcher employed the Achievement Test (AT). The Achievement Test is a collection of verbal evaluation questions from the study's content area that were created by the researcher. Using a table of specifications derived from the topics covered in the experiment, the objects were created. Test-retest was used in determining the reliability index of the instrument. The scores obtained from the two administrations are then compared using correlation coefficients (Pearson's correlation) to determine the level of agreement between the measurements. A correlation of 0.78 indicates good pretest and post-test reliability.

The study included two different teaching methods. The treatment group was taught using the play approach, whereas the control group was taught using the traditional (chalk-talk) method. The curriculum and learning goals that were taught to the two groups were the same. Teachers in the schools who received training on the most effective implementation of the methods were used by the researcher. Both the treatment and control groups were given a pre-test at the beginning of the experiment. The researcher's assistants were the educators in the schools that were sampled. The school schedule was used to conduct the experiment during regular school hours. The post-test was given to the participants in both groups by the researcher

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at the conclusion of the eight-week experiment. The research questions and hypotheses were determined using the information gathered from the pretest and posttest.

The data collected was analyzed using mean difference for research question 1 and 2 while t-test was used to analyze the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 25 was used compute and analyzed the data.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the effect of play way method and conventional teaching method in the pre-test mean scores of pupils among Nursery school pupils in Gombe Metropolis?

Table1: Descriptive Statistics of mean of the pre-test scores of Experimental and Control Group

Variables Group	N	Pre-test mean	t-value	Mean diff.
Control	22	5.2	0.18	0.4
Experimental	23	4.8	1.55	

From these statistics presented in table 1 above, the results shows that the average score on the pre-test for the control group is 5.2, while for the experimental group, is slightly lower at 4.8. This suggests that pupils in the Control group had slightly higher initial scores on the pre-test with mean difference of 0.4, indicating a slight improvement in scores compared to the experimental group.

Research Question 2

What is the mean Performance scores of pupils taught using Play-way method and those exposed to conventional method in Gombe metropolis?

Table 2: Analysis of post-test mean score of students using conventional teaching method and play-way method

Variables Group	N	Posttest Mean	t-value	Mean diff
Control	22	7.2	0.15	2
Experimental	23	9.2	2.31	

Table 2 presents the results of a t-test analysis of the post-test mean scores of students using the control group and the experimental group. The mean of 7.2 with t value of 0.15 yielded from the control group compared with the mean score of 9.2 with the t value of 2.31 from experimental group which yielded higher achievements, therefore experimental group is superior to control group in facilitating achievement among pupils.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean Performance scores of amle and female pupils taught using Play-way method in Gombe metropolis

Table 3: Test of hypothesis for the gender difference in the post test mean score of pupils

Variables Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.
Experimental	Male	12	9.33	1.15	0.293	0.724
	Female	11	9.00	1.41		

Table 3 presents the t-values for male and female pupils. The t-value of the experimental group of 0.2930 with significance level of 0.724 which is also greater than the alpha level of 0.05 indicated that the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught using conventional and play way method is not statistically significant. hence, the decision accept the null hypothesis indicating that there is no significant difference in the gender difference of the post-test analysis using the play way teaching method and the conventional teaching method.

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Discussion of Findings

Based on research findings, it was established that pupils in the Conventional Teaching group had slightly higher initial scores on the pre-test in the first finding, indicating a slight improvement in scores compared to the play way method. Although not significant but may be as a result of individual differences that are naturally present within the members of the groups. The second finding indicated a significant difference between conventional teaching methods and play-way teaching methods in early childhood education. The findings showed that the treatment administer yielded great significance using the play-way teaching methods, which emphasize active learning through play, tend to result in higher levels of engagement and motivation among young learners. Play is intrinsically motivating for children and can stimulate their curiosity, exploration, and creativity which agreed with (Evgenia, 2014). Similarly, Ameena (2020) found that play-based approaches cater to the holistic development of children, including physical, cognitive, social, emotional, and creative aspects. By integrating different domains of development, play-way teaching methods provide a well-rounded educational experience.

The third finding revealed that Male pupils in the post test performed slightly better than their female counterparts in both conventional and play way methods, however the test of significance showed that the difference is not statistically significant. This is in tandem with Popoola (2014) who reported that gender does not have any significant difference on achievement and Iroegbu (2017) who also established that play way teaching method could be used advantageously for the teaching of all children (male and female) without any adverse learning effect.

Conclusion

The study's findings indicated that the play-method provided great performance when compared to conventional teaching techniques. The belief that children acquire the majority of the knowledge they require about the world through play has persisted for a long time. Play can provide the groundwork for healthy physical development, the improvement of fine and gross motor abilities, and overall happiness. The play-way approach is the best way for young children in early childhood programs to develop and learn given the enormous developmental benefits that play provides during a child's early years. The most fascinating and natural process is probably play. Therefore, the play-based technique of instruction is essential for holistic development and for maximizing a child's learning potential.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made: -

1. Encourage Play-Based Learning: Educators should incorporate more play-based learning activities into their curriculum. Provide opportunities for children to engage in imaginative play, hands-on activities, and collaborative games that foster active learning and exploration.
2. Provide a Playful Learning Environment: Create a classroom environment that is conducive to play-based learning. Arrange materials and learning centers that promote open-ended play, creativity, and problem-solving. Incorporate age-appropriate toys, games, and manipulative that encourage exploration and discovery.
3. Professional Development for Teachers: Offer professional development opportunities for teachers to learn about play-way teaching methods and how to effectively implement them in the classroom. Provide training on designing play-based activities, observing and scaffolding children's play, and assessing learning outcomes in a playful context.

References

- Al-Shuaibi A. (2014). The Importance of Education. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260075970_The_Importance_of_Education.
- Evgenia T. (2014) Early years education: are young students intrinsically or extrinsically motivated towards school activities? A discussion about the effects of rewards on young children's learning Metropolitan College, Athens, Greece. *Research In Teacher Education* Vol.4, No.1. April 2014, pp. 17–21.
- Fesseha, E., & Pyle, A. (2016). Conceptualizing play-based learning from kindergarten teachers' perspectives. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 24(3), 361-377.
- Iroegbu, V. (2017). The effect of play-way teaching strategy on primary school pupils' acquisition of Basic science concepts. *Advance in social science research journal* , 4 (10), 120-129.
- Kanal N. (2018) What is Play-Way Method of Learning? Ed tech review, retrieved from <https://www.edtechreview.in/> on 7th of September, 2023.

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- Lalani, A. P. (2020). Play-based Curriculum and the Holistic Development of the Child.
- Margo A. M., & Thomas E. S. (2000). *The Inclusive Classroom: Strategies for effective Instruction*. 3rd Edition, Mastropieri
- Oluseyi M. O. and Ishola S., (2015). Teachers' Instructional Style Preference and Pupils' Academic Achievement in Ibadan: Another Angle to the Knowledge *Asian Journal of Education and e-Learning Volume 03 – Issue 03, June 2015*.Pg. 196-201
- Paolo M. P., Elena F., Elena P., Jonathan B., & Luigi G. (2013). *Handbook of Research on Didactic Strategies and Technologies for Education: Incorporating Advancement (2 Volumes)*. Pg. 829
- Popoola, A.A. (2014). Effects of play-way method on the numeracy skills of early basic education pupils in Ekiti State. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(10), 318-324
- Prout, A., & James, A. (2015). A new paradigm for the sociology of childhood? Provenance, promise and problems. In *Constructing and reconstructing childhood* (pp. 6-28). Routledge.
- Teaching. (2023, May 27). In *Wikipedia*. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teaching>